

KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE, AND PRACTICES OF COMMUNITY PHARMACY STAFF TOWARD COVID-19 VACCINATION AND ADVERSE EVENTS IN THE TWIN CITIES OF PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Background Since the emergence of COVID-19, caused by the SARS-CoV-2, vaccine development is expanded. However, inappropriate and without risk assessment vaccine administration, and lack of awareness of vaccination-related adverse drug effects (ADRs) by community pharmacists have a negative impact on the patient's quality of life. The current study aims to assess knowledge, attitude and perception of community pharmacy staff towards the COVID-19 vaccination and related adverse effect

Method: This is a cross-sectional survey-based study that was conducted between October and November 2022.

Results: There were 400 respondents with 59% males and more than 65% female between the ages of 25 and 39 years. More than 67% of the respondents considered themselves as vaccinated against the COVID-19 vaccine. More than half of the responders 62% were motivated to be involved in citizen's vaccination work. Approximately, 66% of pharmacy staff believed that they could prevent the spread of COVID-19 infection. One of the most vaccine related ADRs influencing factors is the lack of awareness.

Conclusion: The findings of the current study revealed that overall pharmacy staff has better knowledge, attitude and practice towards COVID-19 vaccines and there was significant difference in pharmacist knowledge compared to other health care workers regarding vaccination. Furthermore, improvements in their knowledge will lead to a better implementation of the immunization services.

INTRODUCTION

The respiratory infection caused by coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) has paralyzed the world and was declared a pandemic by The COVID-19 Pandemic, by World Health Organization (WHO). Symptoms

may vary from mild discomfort to serious illness from 2 to 14 days after virus exposure, may start to develop including fever or chills, loss of taste or smell cough, muscle or body aches, shortness of breath,

headache, fatigue and sore throat (Ali mohamadi et al.,2020). The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the weaknesses and vulnerabilities of global health systems and stirred social inequalities. Due to extended shutdowns brought on by the pandemic, some people have lost their jobs, which had a negative ripple effect on the world economy (Chahine, 2020, Visacri et al., 2021). Throughout the pandemic, pharmacies, which are easily accessible healthcare points, have been the major source of updated and authentic information. Furthermore, consequent to social isolation, home delivery for medication and telehealth services are few novel and adapted services provided by pharmacies around the world. The existing literature corroborates immunization services provided by community pharmacists at pharmacies in high-income countries. Community pharmacists have been an effective deterrent to containing the impact of the pandemic by providing pharmaceutical care, updated guidance, and immunization support to the public. In a cross-sectional study of 130 pharmacists from Northern Ireland, 80.7% were willing to administer the COVID-19 vaccination. Another study from Puerto Rico noted a 76.1% willingness of pharmacists to administer the COVID-19 vaccination. Thus, we acknowledge pharmacists' role in major public health crises. A recent survey of public health leaders identified pharmacists as playing a key role in COVID-19 vaccine administration and pandemic planning (Alshahrani et al., 2022). Evidence in published medical literature suggests that pharmacies are uniquely positioned to influence previously difficult-to-reach populations. A review of pharmacy-led immunization programs concluded that pharmacies might be especially effective in immunizing high-risk, older adults who are more likely to need prescription medications and, therefore, use pharmacy services (Gharaibeh et al., 2022, Jairoun et al., 2022)

In Pakistan, COVID-19 also became a significant source of un-employment (Wang et al., 2021). All kind of business, education centers, imports and exports, flights and public transportation were halted. Confirmed or suspected cases of mild sickness were isolated at home. Patients were advised to wear a simple surgical mask and maintain proper cough hygiene (Hafeez et al., 2020). Pakistan, being a

budget-constrained country, spends only 0.6% of its Gross Domestic Product (GDP) on health and thus lags in the provision of basic health infrastructure, latest treatment modalities, and healthcare workforce. Community pharmacy services are underdeveloped in Pakistan owing to weak regulatory mechanisms, non-availability of pharmacists at pharmacies, and minimal government attention, and hence little prepared for COVID-19 atrocities as compared to the developed world. An online cross-sectional survey of 393 community pharmacists from two provinces of Pakistan elucidated good knowledge but poor attitude and practices regarding COVID-19.

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Methodology

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Sample size was calculated using Rao soft calculator at confidence level of 95% with 5% margin of error and sample size was 400. Convenient sampling technique was used

Study design, setting and respondents

A descriptive cross sectional study design was used. Study site for this research included community pharmacies located in twin cities of Pakistan. Study respondents were community pharmacy staff which includes pharmacist, pharmacy technicians and dispensers.

Study Tool

A Pre-validated questionnaire was used to assess the pre-existing knowledge of pharmacy staff in the community pharmacy, as well as its correlating influence on attitude and practice and its adverse events towards the COVID-19 vaccines.

Research ethics

The Ethical Committee of Hamdard University (BASR) approved this study

Pharmacist eligibility and recruitment

Inclusion criteria

All community pharmacy staff who gave consent for participation was included in the study.

Exclusion criteria

Industrial pharmacist, academic pharmacist and hospital pharmacist were excluded from study.

Data collection procedures and analysis

Data was collected by the principal investigator trained by the supervisor. Questionnaires were self-administered and collected on the same day to avoid biasness. The data was cleaned, coded and entered in SPSS version 26.0. The frequency and percentages were calculated by using descriptive statistics.

Data storage

All data collection forms were kept in a secure setting, only available to the principal investigator

Results

Demographic Characteristics

Knowledge of Pharmacy staff towards COVID -19 vaccines

Attitudes of pharmacy staff towards covid-19 vaccines

Practices of pharmacy staff towards COVID-19

Phase II Adverse events related to vaccines (COVID-19)

ADR Reporting of COVID-19 vaccines

Chi Square Association comparison between Knowledge related questions and community pharmacy Staff towards COVID -19 vaccines

Indicator	n (%) Yes	n (%) No	P value
Have you heard about the COVID-19 vaccine			0.00
Pharmacist	138(36.7)	1(16.8)	
Pharmacy technicians	119(31.6)	9(31.2)	
Dispenser	119(31.6)	14(52)	
COVID-19 is caused by beta coronavirus			0.00
Pharmacist	116(39.6)	2(1.5)	
Pharmacy technicians	113(38.6)	38(35.9)	
Dispenser	64(21.8)	67(62.6)	
Adherence to COVID-19 vaccination			0.00
Pharmacist	115(42.8)	4(3.7)	
Pharmacy technicians	98(36.4)	51(39.9)	
Dispenser	56(20.8)	75(57.3)	
What do you think about the dosage schedule of COVID-19 vaccine			0.00
Pharmacist	115(40.9)	14(11.8)	
Pharmacy technicians	110(39.1)	30(25.2)	
Dispenser	56(19.9)	75(63.0)	
The COVID-19 vaccination reduce the threats of contracting illness by enhancing the natural defense of the body			0.00
Pharmacist	110(40.3)	14(11.0)	
Pharmacy technicians	91(33.3)	54(42.5)	

Dispenser	72(26.4)	59(46.5)	
Do you know approved brands of COVID-19 vaccines			0.03
Pharmacist	100(36.4)	24(19.2)	
Pharmacy technicians	92(33.5)	53(42.4)	
Dispenser	83(30.2)	48(38.4)	
Every vaccine must undergo extensive and rigorous testing prior to its introduction.			0.00
Pharmacist	107(39.8)	17(13)	
Pharmacy technicians	88(32.7)	57(43.5)	
Dispenser	74(27.5)	57(43.5)	
Any clinically significant adverse event must be reported by pharmacy staff after administration of the COVID -19 vaccine			0.00
Pharmacist	107(41.3)	32(22.7)	
Pharmacy technicians	92(35.5)	38(27)	
Dispenser	60(23.2)	71(50.4)	
Do you have updated information of COVID-19 vaccines			0.00
Pharmacist	99(38.4)	25(17.6)	
Pharmacy technicians	93(36)	52(36.6)	
Dispenser	66(25.6)	65(45.8)	

Chi Square Association between Attitudes related questions and community pharmacy Staff

Indicator
Are you willing to receive COVID-19 vaccination
Pharmacist
Pharmacy technicians
Dispenser
Willingness to participate in community vaccination
Pharmacist
Pharmacy technicians
Dispenser
Willingness of pharmacist to vaccinate public permitted
Pharmacist
Pharmacy technicians
Dispenser
Spread of COVID-19 can be prevented by vaccination
Pharmacist
Pharmacy technicians
Dispenser

Vaccination can completely control COVID-19 infection
Pharmacist
Pharmacy technicians
Dispenser
I think pharmacy staff need complete COVID -19 vaccination information
Pharmacist
Pharmacy technicians
Dispenser

Chi Square association between practices related questions and community pharmacy Staff

Variables	Yes	No	P. Value
Are you willing to receive COVID-19 vaccination			0.00
Pharmacist	99(43.8)	25(14.4)	
Pharmacy technicians	93(41.2)	52(29.9)	
Dispenser	34(15)	97(55.7)	
Do you know how to administer Covid-19 vaccine			0.00
Pharmacist	107(40.8)	17(12.3)	
Pharmacy technicians	98(37.4)	47(34.1)	
Dispenser	57(21.8)	74(53.6)	
Gowns, gloves, and masks must be used while interacting with COVID-19 patients			0.00
Pharmacist	108(38.7)	16(13.2)	
Pharmacy technicians	97(34.8)	48(39.7)	
Dispenser	74(26.5)	57(47.1)	
Do you think special area required in pharmacies for patient vaccination and counseling			0.06
Pharmacist	90(34.6)	34(24.3)	
Pharmacy technicians	80(30.8)	65(46.4)	
Dispenser	90(34.6)	41(29.3)	
Immune response of the vaccine recipient may be affected by improper storage of COVID-19 vaccines			0.00
Pharmacist	99(36.9)	25(18.9)	
Pharmacy technicians	82(30.6)	63(47.7)	
Dispenser	87(32.5)	44(33.3)	
It is necessary to use hand sanitizer after vaccination?			0.00
Pharmacist	101(40.1)	23(15.5)	
Pharmacy technicians	81(32.1)	64(43.2)	
Dispenser	70(27.8)	61(41.2)	

Chi Square Association between ADRs related questions and community pharmacy Staff

Variables	Yes	No	P.Value
What do you think about the safety of COVID-19 vaccine			0.12
Pharmacist	100(35.5)	24(20.3)	
Pharmacy technicians	96(34)	49(41.5)	

Dispenser	86(30.5)	45(38.1)	
Do you know any adverse events related to COVID-19 vaccine?			0.00
Pharmacist	106(35.6)	18(17.6)	
Pharmacy technicians	103(34.6)	42(41.2)	
Dispenser	89(29.9)	42(41.2)	
Wheezing side effects			0.00
Pharmacist	85(36.8)	39(23.1)	
Pharmacy technicians	65(28.1)	80(47.3)	
Dispenser	81(35.1)	50(29.6)	
Swelling of lips face and throat			0.02
Pharmacist	95(37)	29(20.3)	
Pharmacy technicians	87(33.9)	58(40.6)	
Dispenser	75(29.2)	56(39.2)	
Epileptic seizure			0.94
Pharmacist	74(35.7)	50(25.9)	
Pharmacy technicians	68(32.9)	77(39.9)	
Dispenser	65(31.4)	66(34.2)	
Fatigue			0.45
Pharmacist	97(32.8)	29(27.9)	
Pharmacy technicians	95(32.1)	48(46.2)	
Dispenser	104(35.1)	27(26)	
Injection size reactions			0.39
Pharmacist	89(33.1)	35(26.7)	
Pharmacy technicians	86(32)	59(45)	
Dispenser	94(34.9)	37(28.2)	
Irritation			0.14
Pharmacist	74(34.9)	50(26.6)	
Pharmacy technicians	69(32.5)	76(40.4)	
Dispenser	69(32.5)	62(33)	
Headache			0.01
Pharmacist	110(35.5)	14(15.6)	
Pharmacy technicians	108(34.8)	37(41.1)	
Dispenser	92(29.7)	39(43.3)	
Heart Burn			0.18
Pharmacist	102(37)	35(29.4)	
Pharmacy technicians	88(31.9)	55(46.2)	
Dispenser	86(31.2)	29(24.4)	
Shortness of breath			0.03
Pharmacist	96(35.7)	33(25.2)	
Pharmacy technicians	82(30.5)	63(48.1)	

Dispenser	91(33.8)	35(26.7)	
Patient doesn't get vaccine because of fear of side effects			0.00
Pharmacist	107(43.3)	17(11.1)	
Pharmacy technicians	88(35.6)	57(37.3)	
Dispenser	52(21.1)	79(51.6)	
Do you know how to manage ADR of COVID-19 vaccine			0.00
Pharmacist	117(39.4)	7(6.8)	
Pharmacy technicians	99(33.3)	46(44.7)	
Dispenser	81(27.3)	50(48.5)	

Chi Square Association between ADR reporting related questions and community pharmacy Staff

Indicator	Yes	No	P.Value
I believe that the adverse drug reaction ADR reporting is an important activity to improve safety of Vaccine			0.00
Pharmacist	88(39.1)	36(20.6)	
Pharmacy technicians	78(34.7)	67(38.3)	
Dispenser	59(26.2)	72(41.1)	
Educational background has provided me with enough information about reporting of ADRs in Pakistan			0.00
Pharmacist	89(38.9)	35(20.5)	
Pharmacy technicians	82(35.8)	63(36.8)	
Dispenser	58(25.3)	73(42.7)	
Adverse drug reaction reporting is a professional responsibly			0.00
Pharmacist	103(39.8)	21(14.9)	
Pharmacy technicians	91(35.1)	54(38.3)	
Dispenser	65(25.1)	66(46.8)	
I consider myself as important health care worker for reporting an ADR			0.00
Pharmacist	100(41)	23(14.8)	
Pharmacy technicians	81(33.2)	64(41.3)	
Dispenser	63(25.8)	68(43.9)	
Reporting an ADR should be promoted by workplace			0.00
Pharmacist	109(40.8)	17(13.7)	
Pharmacy technicians	98(34.2)	45(36.3)	
Dispenser	69(25)	62(50)	
Do you keep records of ADR?			0.19
Pharmacist	112(42.1)	22(24.7)	

Pharmacy technicians	94(24.8)	39(43.8)	
Dispenser	103(33.1)	28(31.5)	
Have you reported suspected ADR to manufacturer or DRAP?			0.00
Pharmacist	74(41.8)	50(22.4)	
Pharmacy technicians	59(33.3)	86(38.6)	
Dispenser	44(24.9)	87(39)	

DISCUSSION

This was the first research to evaluate the knowledge, attitude and skills of pharmacy staff in Pakistan to provide COVID -19 immunization. Community pharmacy staff has started to play their role in COVID-19 vaccination, resulting in increased vaccination rate. In our study, pharmacy staff has better knowledge about COVID-19 vaccinations showing (67.25%) of adherence, and (70.25%) were aware of dosage scheduled as well. In our study around 67.25% were in favor of vaccine immunization however in another study conducted in Asia in which more than 95% of the healthcare workers surveyed were willing to be vaccinated(Chew et al., 2021).In our study among pharmacy staff pharmacist was more inclined towards COVID-19 vaccination as compared to other staff members. It suggests that pharmacists know more about COVID-19 vaccinations than others. South and Southeast Asia had the greatest vaccination uptake (> 95 %) because pharmacist believed that the pandemic was serious and vaccines were safe (Roncero et al., 2022). Similar to another study confirmed that pharmacists in Vietnam at large possess better understanding about vaccinations. (93.4%), which aligned with the findings of studies conducted in Lebanon (> 90%) (Zeenny et al., 2020), Cairo (83%) (Hamza et al., 2021), Pakistan (84%) (Hussain et al., 2020), but higher than the results of Addis Ababa (53.2%) (Yimenu et al., 2020). The goal of vaccination was to protect recipients and their families, whereas others who resisted thought vaccination was unnecessary. More than 60% of pharmacy personnel were familiar with COVID-19 vaccines, their brands, and how they protect the body by working in tandem with the body's natural defenses and 60% of pharmacy staff has updated information of COVID-19 vaccines. Overall pharmacy staff has better knowledge about

COVID19 vaccines while pharmacists are much more knowledgeable than other staff members about COVID-19 vaccines. In agreement with this study's findings, previous studies conducted in different Asian countries (Zhong et al., 2020; Azlan et al., 2020; Saqlain et al., 2020), Egypt, Kenya and Nigeria (Abdel hafiz et al., 2020; Austrian et al., 2020; Olapegba, 2020) indicated high COVID-19 knowledge among pharmacist about vaccines. During the analysis of the attitude of the pharmacy staff, more than 60% of pharmacy staff believed that COVID-19 can be fully controlled. A significant portion of them were influenced to be part of vaccination at community level and believed that vaccination can prevent spread of COVID -19. The majority of pharmacists are ready to vaccinate the public if vaccination by a pharmacist is permitted. A number of respondents also believed that community pharmacy staff must have all the relevant information regarding COVID-19 vaccine and as a result of comparison between pharmacy staff pharmacist have a significantly positive attitude towards COVID-19 vaccines in comparison to other pharmacy staff. Similar to findings, Vietnamese pharmacists might undertake a variety of roles and contribute significantly to the combat against the COVID -19 pandemic.(Nguyen et al., 2021). Similarly in another study between June and July 2020 in Egypt, knowledge, attitudes, and practices of Egyptian population; pharmacists evaluated that about 64% of the participants showed positive attitudes towards the Egyptian ministry of health in controlling the pandemic which was slight higher than our studies (Galal et al., 2021).During the analysis of the practice of the pharmacy staff towards COVID-19 vaccines when dealing with COVID-19 patients, 70% of pharmacy staff used gowns, gloves, and masks, and 65% of pharmacy staff think that

pharmacies need a special area for patient vaccination and counseling. 63% of people believe it is necessary to use hand sanitizer after receiving a vaccination, and 67% think inappropriate COVID-19 vaccine storage may influence the immune response of vaccine recipients. The current study's findings also shown that, in comparison to other pharmacy staff members such as pharmacy technicians and dispensers, pharmacists has acceptable knowledge regarding the administration of the COVID-19 vaccine. Similar to another study conducted in Poland revealed that majority of the pharmacists had adequate knowledge regarding COVID-19 vaccination and were providing effective immunization services during pandemic (Lindner-Pawłowicz et al., 2021). During analysis of ADRs related to COVID-19 vaccines 75% of pharmacy staff thinks that COVID-19 vaccination is safe with some side effects, and 74% are aware of how to deal with any adverse reactions related to COVID-19 vaccine. A considerable proportion of them were prepared to handle major vaccine adverse events, and a number of responders were also aware of how to treat minor COVID-19 vaccination adverse events. Also, the results showed 60% of the participants might be discouraged from vaccination because of fear of ADRs of vaccines. This finding is similar to our previous findings in (Akhmetzhanova et al., 2020) as well as others including that of Omer et al., 2021 who suggest patients were more vaccine resistant because of fear of adverse effects related to vaccines. This study further investigated the KAP of community pharmacy workers in terms of ADR reporting. In the current study, 56.3% response rate was observed in contrast to this a higher response rate (82%) was seen in another study by Piparyia et al 2020. A lower response rate (21.8%) was reported by Srikanth et al (Srikanth and Adepu, 2014, Alam et al., 2021). The majority of participants were having a positive view about pharmacovigilance. A 61.2% pharmacy staff thought that it was important to report adverse drug reactions (ADRs) because of importance of pharmacovigilance program. The significant respondent (77.8%) kept records of ADR and forwarded the detailed report to ADR reporting center. Similar finding was also reported in various studies which are showcasing agreement with our results (Li et al., 2018). Education and regular

training for pharmacy employees may help in pharmacovigilance program success and build a spontaneous ADR reporting system in Pakistan (Desai et al., 2011).

Limitations of the study

The results of the current study are restricted to twin cities in Pakistan and may not be applicable to any other regions of the country so similar type of work can be performed in other regions of the country for better understanding of the concept.

Conclusion

The findings of the current study revealed that overall pharmacy staff has better knowledge, attitude and practice towards COVID-19 vaccines and this could be because pharmacy workers had a rudimentary understanding of these services with basic trainings. However there was significant difference in pharmacist knowledge and preparedness as compared to other health care workers for immunization services in the community setups. This might be due to the fact that basic concepts of immunization are incorporated in the curriculum of pharmacy so pharmacist has basic knowledge regarding immunization. In order to improve knowledge of other pharmacy staff, a number of changes are required, including updating of the pharmacy curriculum taught, implementation of international standards for pharmacy practice, training and integration of pharmacy staff fully into the healthcare system. Furthermore, health care staff should dispel patients concerns about COVID-19 vaccines. If any untoward adverse event occurs, the report must be submitted to ADR reporting center. The results of the present study showed that improvement in their knowledge will lead to better implementation of the immunization services.

Disclosure of potential conflicts of interest

No potential conflicts of interest were disclosed.

Future Recommendations

Various factors in community pharmacies settings should be studied separately with the purpose of developing interventions for improving knowledge, practice and attitude of pharmacy.

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